

The effects of slow wave sleep characteristics on semantic, episodic, and procedural memory in people with epilepsy

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13 **Keywords: epilepsy, slow wave sleep, episodic memory, procedural memory, declarative**
14 **memory, anti-seizure medication.**

15 Abstract

16 Slow wave sleep (SWS) is highly relevant for verbal and non-verbal/spatial memory in healthy
17 individuals, but also in people with epilepsy. However, contradictory findings exist regarding the
18 effect of seizures on overnight memory retention, particularly relating to procedural and non-verbal
19 memory, and thorough examination of episodic memory retention with ecologically valid tests is
20 missing. This research explores the interaction of SWS duration with epilepsy-relevant factors, as
21 well as the relation of spectral characteristics of SWS on overnight retention of procedural, verbal,
22 and episodic memory.

23 In an epilepsy monitoring unit, epilepsy patients (N=40) underwent learning, immediate and 12h
24 delayed testing of memory retention for a fingertapping task (procedural memory), a word-pair task
25 (verbal memory), and an innovative virtual reality task (episodic memory). We used multiple linear
26 regression to examine the impact of SWS duration, spectral characteristics of SWS, seizure
27 occurrence, medication, depression, seizure type, gender, and epilepsy duration on overnight memory
28 retention.

29 Results indicated that none of the candidate variables significantly predicted overnight changes for
30 procedural memory performance. For verbal memory, the occurrence of tonic-clonic seizures
31 negatively impacted memory retention and higher psychoactive medication load showed a tendency
32 for lower verbal memory retention. Episodic memory was significantly impacted by epilepsy
33 duration, displaying a potential nonlinear impact with a longer duration than 10 years negatively
34 affecting memory performance. Higher drug load of anti-seizure medication was by tendency related
35 to better overnight retention of episodic memory. Contrary to expectations longer SWS duration

36 showed a trend towards decreased episodic memory performance. Analyses on associations between
37 memory types and EEG band power during SWS revealed lower alpha-band power in the frontal
38 right region as significant predictor for better episodic memory retention.

39 In conclusion, this research reveals that memory modalities are not equally affected by important
40 epilepsy factors such as duration of epilepsy and medication, as well as SWS spectral characteristics.

41

42 **1 Introduction**

43 For decades scientists documented the multifaceted effects of epilepsy on memory. Patients might
44 suffer from impaired memory depending on the type of epilepsy (Elger et al., 2004; Muhlert et al.,
45 2011), wherein temporal lobe epilepsy has repeatedly been shown to impair verbal memory
46 performance (Helmstaedter, 2002). Notably, memory impairments may be caused by additional
47 factors, such as the location of the seizure onset zone (Wilkinson et al., 2012), type and frequency of
48 seizures (Wilkinson et al., 2012; Höller and Trinka, 2015), amount, type, and timing of interictal
49 epileptic activity (Holmes and Lenck-Santini, 2006; Binnie, 2003; Fitzgerald et al., 2013), anti-
50 seizure medication taken (Motamedi and Meador, 2004; Jokeit, Hennric et al., 2005; Höller et al.,
51 2020a), age of epilepsy onset (Thompson, P. J. and Corcoran, 1992), and comorbidities of psychiatric
52 nature (Rayner and Tailby, 2017) such as depression (Brown et al., 1994) among others. Even a
53 longitudinal decline of memory in a dementia-like manner was postulated, but only a high life-time
54 number of tonic-clonic seizures exhibited such an effect (Dodrill, 1986).

55 Additionally, memory modalities may be differently affected by epilepsy-relevant factors.
56 Specifically, verbal memory is frequently documented to be impaired in patients with temporal lobe
57 epilepsy (Helmstaedter, 2002). The situation is, however, more complex than the old and frequently
58 criticized “phrenological thinking” might suggest (Baxendale, 2018; Rayner and Tailby, 2017). This
59 approach assumes that epileptic activity in one brain region affects memory that depends on the very
60 same structure (Baxendale, 2018; Rayner and Tailby, 2017). Today, epilepsy is recognized as a
61 network disease (Kramer and Cash, 2012), and the representation of memory is also understood to
62 involve a complex network of cortical and subcortical components (McNaughton and Vann, 2022).
63 Thus, multiple memory modalities can be affected by localized epileptic activity. For example, in
64 addition to verbal memory, also episodic memory is affected in temporal lobe epilepsy
65 (Helmstaedter, 2002).

66 To document the multifaceted problems of memory retention in people with epilepsy, a multitude of
67 neuropsychological tests can be utilized (Baxendale et al., 2019; Wilson et al., 2015). However, these
68 tests are usually completed in a single session with little time separating learning and delayed
69 memory testing. It is increasingly recognized that people with epilepsy suffer from accelerated
70 forgetting, impaired retention, or impaired consolidation (Cassel and Kopelman, 2019;
71 Mameniskiene et al., 2006; Kapur et al., 1997; Fitzgerald et al., 2013; Butler and Zeman, 2008; Blake
72 et al., 2000) Consequently, the validity of evaluating memory performance during a single session is
73 put into question by evidence that self-rated memory performance correlates with recall after long
74 delays (e.g. days), but not after a 30min delay (Fitzgerald et al., 2013). Accelerated long-term
75 forgetting and remote memory impairment cannot be sufficiently determined by standard memory
76 tests (Butler and Zeman, 2008). It is therefore important to investigate long-term retention in people
77 with epilepsy, as well as the variables that undermine the patients’ capacity to consolidate and retain
78 memory.

79 Sleep between learning and recall supports memory performance in healthy participants (Born et al.,
80 2006), during which cardinal sleep oscillations facilitate reactivation of previously acquired
81 information and memory consolidation processes (Gais and Born, 2004; Ficca et al., 2000). Sleep-
82 dependent memory consolidation depends on the type of memory and the sleep architecture.
83 Specifically, procedural memory (Schönauer et al., 2014), but also declarative and emotional
84 memories were shown to benefit from sleep between learning and recall, with slow wave sleep
85 (SWS) benefiting declarative memories more while rapid eye movement sleep enhances procedural
86 and emotional memory (Diekelmann et al., 2009). Furthermore, sleep spindles were associated with
87 better procedural memory consolidation (van Schalkwijk et al., 2020; Boutin et al., 2024; Kumral et
88 al., 2023).

89 People with epilepsy are vulnerable to effects of impaired sleep-dependent memory consolidation
90 (Latreille et al., 2022) because of the bi-directional relationship between epilepsy and sleep (Malow,
91 2007) and, more specifically, because of the negative effects of epilepsy on sleep architecture
92 including fragmentation of slow wave sleep (López-Gomáriz et al., 2004). Among these effects,
93 sleep-dependent interictal epileptiform events particularly during non-REM sleep (Halász et al.,
94 2019; Urbain et al., 2011; Bjørnæs et al., 2013; Galer et al., 2015) and sleep-related seizures (Malow,
95 2007) partly explain hampered sleep-related memory consolidation in people with epilepsy.
96 Additionally, anti-seizure drugs impact brain activity e.g. by increasing or decreasing power in
97 specific frequency bands (Höller et al., 2018; Höller and Nardone, 2021) and they can change sleep
98 architecture by extending or shortening specific sleep stages (Carvalho et al., 2022). Thus, it is
99 plausible that anti-seizure drugs also impact sleep-related consolidation of memory, but the exact
100 nature of this relationship is poorly understood.

101 Among patients with left-lateralized temporal lobe epilepsy, verbal memory decays at an increased
102 rate when a seizure occurs in the 24h between learning and recall (Jokeit, H. et al., 2001). In N=8
103 patients with transient epileptic amnesia (Atherton et al., 2014) and in a similarly small sample of
104 N=7 patients with temporal lobe epilepsy (Deak et al., 2011), it was found that verbal memory
105 decayed more rapidly as compared to healthy control subjects during daytime retention, whereas no
106 group differences were observed for overnight memory retention. In the whole group, verbal memory
107 performance was significantly correlated with the percent of SWS in the entire night, but not in the
108 subgroups, since they were too small (Deak et al., 2011). In another study, SWS duration in healthy
109 controls was shown to be correlated with sleep-related benefits on overnight retention of verbal
110 memory, whereas no correlation was observed in people with epilepsy (Atherton et al., 2016). The
111 fact that multiple studies did not find nighttime sleep architecture to be related with memory
112 retention in people with epilepsy (Fitzgerald et al., 2013) emphasizes the potential detrimental effects
113 of epilepsy on memory retention.

114 Retention intervals separating learning and recollection are prone to disruptions of memory
115 consolidation processes by epileptiform activity. In a 24h retention interval, patients with temporal
116 lobe epilepsy showed similar performance retention on a fingertapping task as compared to control
117 subjects, but only one patient reported a seizure during this time period (Deak et al., 2011). Indeed, in
118 another study only seizure-free retention periods were associated with improved performance,
119 whereas no performance changes were observed when a seizure occurred during the retention period
120 separating learning and delayed recall (van Schalkwijk et al., 2021). It is therefore important to
121 control for the occurrence of seizures during retention intervals.

122 Finally, non-verbal memory was assessed in a card-position association task in older people with
123 epilepsy, and it was found that 24h retention was significantly predicted by the number of anti-

124 seizure drugs, interictal epileptiform activity, as well as slow wave activity power during non-rapid-
125 eye movement (non-REM) sleep (Sarkis et al., 2023). The importance of slow wave activity has also
126 been documented based on intracranial hippocampal recordings, where delta activity (2-4 Hz) in the
127 hippocampus during non-REM sleep was positively correlated with task performance at retest in a
128 spatial memory task (Moroni et al., 2014). Another study investigated non-verbal declarative
129 memory with pairs of pictures and found that overnight memory retention was positively correlated
130 with the duration of SWS and showed that seizure occurrence impaired memory retention (Sarkis et
131 al., 2016).

132 In summary, sleep plays an important role for the consolidation and retention of verbal, procedural,
133 and non-verbal/spatial memory in people with epilepsy, wherein SWS in particular plays a prominent
134 role for memory consolidation and retention. In contrast, seizures can lead to impaired overnight
135 retention of procedural and non-verbal memory.

136 As a general limitation, the sizes of the patient samples in the studies examining overnight memory
137 retention are all very small, limiting possibilities for statistical assessment of multiple moderating
138 factors of overnight retention and therefore restricting overall conclusions (Latreille et al., 2022). It is
139 still unclear whether SWS duration and spectral characteristics as well as other factors such as
140 medication and seizures during the retention interval impact all memory modalities equally. To date,
141 most studies have restricted themselves to studying the effects of epilepsy on memory retention for
142 one or two memory modalities, and no ecologically valid tests have been employed for episodic
143 memory. In the present study we addressed these issues by investigating a larger sample of people
144 with epilepsy that underwent testing of verbal, procedural, and episodic memory, wherein an
145 innovative and ecologically valid virtual-reality test was implemented to assess episodic memory.
146 We examined whether verbal, procedural, and episodic memory are similarly affected by SWS
147 duration and power spectra of SWS during the retention night, and crucially controlled for seizure
148 occurrence during the retention night, medication (anti-seizure and psychoactive), depression, type of
149 seizure, gender, and duration of epilepsy as the current age minus the age of onset of seizures.

150

151 **2 Materials and Methods**

152 **2.1 Ethics**

153 The ethical commission of the Region of Salzburg, Austria approved the study protocol (approval nr.
154 415-E/1755/20-2016). The study was carried out in agreement with the Declaration of Helsinki. All
155 patients signed written informed consent forms.

156 **2.2 Setting and recruitment**

157 The study took place at the Epilepsy Monitoring Unit (EMU) of the University Clinic for Neurology,
158 Christian Doppler Medical Centre of the Paracelsus Medical University in Salzburg, Austria. The
159 unit consists of four beds and a monitoring room, where trained staff monitor the patients'
160 electroencephalogram (EEG) and video throughout the examination. The daily rhythm in the epilepsy
161 monitoring unit is structured by lights being turned on in the morning (06:30-07:00), breakfast
162 (07:00-07:30), lunch (11.30), dinner (16:30), and lights being turned off in the evening (22:00-
163 00:00). During the monitoring period it is common to taper the dosage of anti-seizure drugs and to
164 expose patients to sleep deprivation in the third night to provoke seizure occurrence. Patients' stay
165 within the EMU typically lasted from Monday until Friday to obtain detailed recordings of suspected

166 seizure events thus facilitating detailed diagnosis of their epilepsy syndrome and presurgical
167 evaluation. Patients with a high likelihood of an epilepsy diagnosis were invited to participate in the
168 study. Further inclusion criteria were age (between 18 and 75 years), fluency in the German
169 language, adequate intellectual ability to give informed consent and perform the memory tasks, and
170 no interfering neurological diseases of degenerative nature. Informed consent was obtained following
171 admittance on Monday morning by medical staff, after which we recorded demographical
172 information and patients were tested for depression with the German version of Beck's Depression
173 Inventory (Hautzinger et al., 2006). EEG was installed by medical technicians and continuously
174 monitored and maintained for the full duration of stay within the EMU. A total of 106 patients were
175 recruited between the 2nd of February 2016 and the 11th of June 2018. Exclusion criteria were
176 experience of status epilepticus during the stay, missing data, as well as unclear diagnosis.

177 **2.3 Procedure**

178 The study involved a total of seven sessions, with two testing sessions per day occurring at 08:00 and
179 19:00. The procedure that started on Monday evening and lasted until Thursday evening. Each
180 session included three memory tasks that concerned verbal, procedural, or episodic memory. With
181 exception of the first, each session started with recollection of task information learned during the
182 previous session, followed by learning the new variations of the three memory tasks and immediate
183 assessment of memory performance (Figure 1).

184 All testing was conducted at bedside using a laptop (17" Lenovo) placed on the patient's bedside
185 table. The table was rotated such that the patient could look straight at the laptop screen and
186 comfortably reach the keyboard.

187 **2.4 Memory Tasks**

188 **2.4.1 Fingertapping task: procedural memory**

189 The fingertapping task is described in full detail in a previous publication arising from the same
190 project where the task was shown to reveal the effect of seizures on offline consolidation of
191 procedural memory during day and night (van Schalkwijk et al., 2021). In short, patients were
192 instructed to type a five-element sequence using four fingers of their non-dominant left hand as
193 quickly and accurately as possible (see Figure 2). The learning session consisted of 12 trials of 30 sec
194 each with inter-trial breaks of 30 sec. Recall sessions had the exact same procedure as learning
195 sessions but consisted of 4 trials. Outcome parameters were the number of completed sequences per
196 trial to indicate speed, and the percent of correctly typed sequences relative to the total keystrokes per
197 trial as accuracy. As a performance measure that integrates speed and accuracy, we measured the
198 number of correctly typed 3-element sequences within a trial (triplets; e.g., for a sequence of 1-4-2-3-
199 1, the triplets were 1-4-2, 4-2-3, 2,3-1, 2-1-1, and 1-1-4). For each outcome measure, we averaged
200 over the last three trials of the respective learning session to get immediate recall performance, and
201 over the last three trials of the following recall session to measure delayed recall performance.
202 Finally, we calculated performance changes from learning in the evening to recall in the morning as a
203 ratio of the number of triplets during delayed recall divided by the number of triplets in the
204 immediate recall.

205

206 **2.4.2 Word-pair task: verbal semantic memory**

207 For the word-pair task, 6 sets of 60 word-pairs were created based on the Berlin Affective Word List
208 (Jacobs et al., 2015; Vö et al., 2009). From the list, we extracted nouns with an emotional valence
209 mean between -1 to $+1$ (overall scale ranges from -3 to $+3$) and an arousal mean of 1.33 to 3.30
210 (overall scale ranges from 1 to 5), with two to three syllables. The 6 lists were balanced for these
211 parameters. Each list consists of 60 word-pairs, of which 30 pairs are semantically related and 30
212 semantically unrelated. During learning, patients were presented with the session-specific word-pair
213 list, wherein singular word-pairs were shown in a fixed order for a duration of 10 sec per pair. To
214 monitor attention and induce a similar learning strategy for all patients, they were instructed to think
215 of a potential connection between the two words and rate the words to be connected or not. For
216 example, word pairs were “glas - water” (related) or “floor - leaf” (unrelated). During recall, patients
217 were shown only the first word of each word pair and were asked to report the second word or
218 indicate that they had forgotten (see Figure 3).

219 A researcher with a copy of the respective word pair list noted whether the answer was correct. Trials
220 were not time restricted and lasted until the participant gave an answer. Like in the fingertapping
221 task, the outcome measure for the word-pair task was the ratio of the number of correctly
222 remembered word-pairs in the morning during delayed recall divided by the number of correctly
223 remembered word-pairs in the immediate recall session in the evening of the day before.

224 **2.4.3 Virtual reality task: episodic memory**

225 The virtual reality task was created for this project in UNITY (Unity Technologies ApS, Engine
226 Version 5.3.5f1, [Unity3d.com](https://unity3d.com)), including several packages (asset store products) to fill the towns
227 with details. The task can be downloaded from the dataset referenced in the manuscript describing it
228 in full detail (Höller et al., 2020b). The task was shown to respond to anti-seizure drug tapering in
229 another publication arising from the same project (Höller et al., 2020a). In short, patients navigated
230 through a virtual town on the computer screen, using the cursor keys on the keyboard to move
231 forward, left, and right. The six towns had only one path that could be followed to explore the
232 environment. Each town included 10 turns (left or right) which we call hereafter “scenes”. Each
233 scene included at least two elements. The towns' paths learned during night 2 and 3 are shown in
234 Figure 4.

235 On the first day, patients completed a practice run in an empty town with no details to become
236 familiar with the navigation. The practice lasted as long as needed to become familiar with the
237 procedure. We examined episodic memory regarding remembered details, egocentric, and allocentric
238 information. During immediate and delayed recall, patients were first asked to name all the elements
239 they could remember, e.g., a car, a hospital, a park, a table. This number of elements constitutes what
240 we denoted as “WHAT” outcome of memory in this task. Then, we requested additional descriptions
241 of each element and counted the number of correctly remembered details. For example, if a patient
242 indicated remembering a table, they would describe it by color, shape, texture, etc. The description of
243 a hospital could include a red cross at the front of the building, number of floors, etc. The number of
244 correctly remembered details constituted the “DETAILS” outcome of memory performance. Next,
245 we asked for each remembered element when the patients would have seen it in the town, with the
246 option to say rather at the beginning, middle, or end of the town. This ordering of elements
247 constitutes the “WHEN” outcome. Based on the total number of scenes in each town, the first three
248 scenes were considered to be at the beginning, the following four as in the middle, and the last three
249 as the end of the town. Furthermore, patients were asked whether they turned left or right after the
250 element. Whether the element was to their left or right constituted the “EGOCENTRIC WHERE”

251 outcome. When patients remembered more than one detail in one scene, patients were asked about
252 the allocation of the details relative to each other, constituting the "ALLOCENTRIC WHERE"
253 outcome. To the numbers noted down for these memory outcome parameters WHAT", "DETAILS",
254 "WHEN", "EGOCENTRIC WHERE", and "ALLOCENTRIC WHERE" , only correct responses
255 were counted. The consensus-based evaluation strategy of the patients' responses is described in
256 further detail in our previous publication (Höller et al., 2020b).

257 To get one single outcome measure, we summed up the correctly remembered items across the
258 subscales "WHAT", "DETAILS", "WHEN", "EGOCENTRIC WHERE", and "ALLOCENTRIC
259 WHERE". Like in the word-pair task, the outcome measure that was submitted to the statistical
260 analysis was the ratio of the number of correctly remembered items in the morning during delayed
261 recall divided by the number of correctly remembered items in the immediate recall session in the
262 evening of the day before.

263 **2.5 Drug load**

264 We determined drug load at admission and on the day preceding the experimental night for
265 psychoactive and anti-seizure drugs. For each drug we calculated the ratio between the prescribed
266 dose and the defined daily dose. Then, we summed the loads over all drugs taken on that day,
267 separately for psychoactive and anti-seizure drugs.

268 **2.6 EEG recording**

269 EEG was continuously recorded throughout the stay in the epilepsy monitoring unit from each
270 patient. The recording was conducted with a routine clinical system (SystemPlus Evolution, SD LTM
271 46 Express Amplifier, Micromed S.p.A, Mogliano, Italy). There were 29 standard electrodes placed
272 according to the 10-20 system, with the Fpz as ground and Oz as reference. At setup on the day of
273 admission, impedances were ensured to be below 10 k Ω and daily monitoring of data and noise in the
274 signal ensured that improvements were made to keep this quality standard. Data were digitized at
275 1,024 Hz and online filtered by 0.1Hz high-pass and 50Hz notch to remove line-noise. Additional
276 electrodes were attached to measure differential electrocardiogram, electromyogram, and
277 electrooculogram. The electromyogram at the chin and additional horizontal electrooculogram
278 electrodes were mounted only in the evening and removed in the morning for the present study to
279 facilitate sleep staging.

280 **2.7 Data selection**

281 For the present study, we discarded the first night because of the well-known bias resulting from
282 habituation of the patient to the recording environment (Mayeli et al., 2022). We aimed at including
283 the data from the second night, thus including learning session 3 with immediate recall 3 and delayed
284 recall 3.1 (see Figure 1). However, if sleep scoring for the second night did not include SWS, the third
285 night was considered for analyses, thus including learning session 5 with immediate recall 5 and
286 delayed recall 5.1 (see Figure 1). The third night was also considered if patients underwent sleep
287 deprivation on the second night. Patients who did not reach SWS or had a viable night without sleep
288 deprivation were excluded from further data analysis.

289 **2.8 Seizure identification**

290 The EMU staff worked in shifts with medical technical nurses working during the day and trained
291 students during the night. Seizure monitoring included the detection of seizures based on EEG and

292 behavioral cues and an ictal testing that evaluated responsivity, sensation and perception,
293 consciousness, memory, and basic cognitive skills as per a standardized testing protocol (Beniczky et
294 al., 2016). The day-shift team routinely screened the 24h EEG and video recordings offline and
295 marked segments with clinical and subclinical seizures, as well as all events that were suspected to be
296 seizures but turned out to be of a different nature. All marked segments were further examined by a
297 neurologist to confirm the markings.

298 For the purpose of this study, a clinically trained EEG technician re-evaluated the occurrence of
299 seizures in the EEG and video and classified the seizures into tonic-clonic seizures and other
300 seizures. Time of seizure onset was compared to the retention interval (i.e., night 2 or 3) to rate if a
301 seizure occurred between learning and recall.

302 **2.9 Slow-wave sleep staging**

303 Sleep staging was performed manually with the aim of identifying SWS, corresponding to stages 3-4
304 in the manual of Rechtschaffen and Kales (Rechtschaffen and Kales, 1968) and stage N3 in the new
305 AASM (American Academy of Sleep Medicine) manual (Iber et al., 2007). To this end, night files
306 were extracted from the clinical system and imported to the software Brain Vision Analyzer (Brain
307 Products GmbH). SWS was identified by scrolling through the EEG in 20 sec epochs as
308 recommended for fragmented sleep (Schulz, 2008). A trained researcher set markers that defined the
309 beginning and end of each segment initially, and all segments were then reviewed by an experienced
310 EEG-researcher. The criterion for SWS was that slow waves of the frequency below 2 Hz with high
311 amplitude, synchronized activity must occupy at least 50% of an epoch (Hori et al., 2001).

312 **2.10 Quantitative EEG-analysis**

313 We analyzed SWS segments quantitatively in two ways. First, we extracted total duration of SWS by
314 summing up the duration of each marked segment in the examined night of a patient. Then, the SWS
315 segments were divided into epochs of 4 sec and each epoch underwent Fast Fourier Transform
316 (resolution 0.25 Hz, non-complex output in microvoltage, half spectrum). The resulting power
317 spectra were averaged across all available epochs and power density was extracted for frequency
318 bands delta (0.5-4 Hz), theta (5-7 Hz), alpha (8-12 Hz), sigma (13-15 Hz), and beta (16-29 Hz) as
319 unsigned, rectified values of mean activity for each band. Finally, we averaged across electrodes for
320 areas frontal left (F3, F7, F11), frontal right (F4, F8, F12), central left (C3), central right (C4),
321 temporal left (T7, T11), temporal right (T8, T12), parietal left (P3, P7, P11), parietal right (P4, P8,
322 P12), occipital left (O1), and occipital right (O2).

323 **2.11 Statistics**

324 All statistics were carried out with R 2022-06-23 in R-Studio version 2022.02.3+492 (R Core Team,
325 2022). We reported median and range for ordinal variables and mean and SD for interval variables.
326 To control for the possible effect of temporal lobe seizures, we reported descriptives for immediate
327 and delayed recall as well as ratios for this sub-samples and compared these values between the two
328 subgroups (temporal lobe seizures vs. other). For the three memory outcome parameters, the ratio
329 between delayed recall in the morning and immediate recall in the evening for fingertapping triplets,
330 word-pairs, and correctly remembered items in the episodic-memory task, we performed multiple
331 linear regression with the R function “lm” to identify significant determinants of memory decline (or
332 improvement) overnight. We conducted this analysis separately for patient characteristics and brain
333 activity during SWS.

334 Candidate predictor variables among patient characteristics were the BDI score, seizure type (focal,
335 generalized), drug load of anti-seizure drugs, drug load of psychoactive drugs, sex, total duration of
336 deep sleep in minutes, whether a seizure occurred during the night, whether a tonic-clonic seizure
337 occurred during the night, and duration of epilepsy as the current age minus the age of onset of
338 seizures. Since this analysis involved three models for the three memory outcomes, the Bonferroni-
339 corrected level of significance was $.05/3$, i.e. the critical alpha level was $p < .017$.

340 Second, we estimated multiple regression models with the same R function “lm” for each frequency
341 band (delta, theta, alpha, sigma, and beta). Candidate predictor variables were EEG power measures
342 in the regions frontal left, frontal right, temporal left, temporal right, parietal left, parietal right,
343 central left, central right, occipital left, and occipital right. Again, we performed Bonferroni-
344 correction, which was applied to the three memory outcomes and the five frequency bands, thus, the
345 critical alpha level of $.05/15$ was $p < .003$.

346 For supporting the visual analysis of statistical trends, we created fitted lines to scatter plots for
347 significant effects based on the R-function “predictdf” which uses a t-based approximation for
348 outliers and the general-linear model (glm) for normal confidence intervals.

349 **3 Results**

350 **3.1 Sample characteristics**

351 From the total sample of 106 patients who were included into the study, the first patient was excluded
352 because of a change of protocol, six patients were excluded because of incomplete EEG data, and
353 five patients needed to be excluded because no SWS was detectable (neither in night 2 nor in night
354 3). Sub-analysis of this sample with respect to the impact of no SWS on memory was not conducted
355 because of the diversity of sleep patterns in this subsample. Specifically, two of them did sleep but
356 did not display any SWS, two of them had very little sleep overall, and one had no sleep at all.
357 Another 10 patients were excluded because the extensive examination in the video-EEG monitoring
358 unit did not lead to a conclusive diagnosis of epilepsy. A total of 11 patients were excluded because
359 the diagnostic procedure led to the conclusion that they did not suffer from epilepsy. Another 6
360 patients were excluded because they underwent brain surgery in the past. The type of surgery and
361 time since surgery was so heterogeneous in this sample that we refrained from a sub-analysis in this
362 sample (4 years ago partial removal of left temporal lobe, 2 years ago unilateral removal of amygdala and
363 part of hippocampus, 1 year ago craniotomy and resection of a cystis, 13 years ago removal of arterial-
364 venous malformation temporo-median parahippocampal left (2x embolisation), 2 years ago removal of
365 dyembryoplastic neuroepithelial tumour, 2 years ago removal of gangliogliom at right gyrus occipitotemoralis
366 medialis). Then, since the fingertapping task was required to be done with the non-dominant left hand,
367 another 7 left-handed patients were excluded. Finally, 20 more patients were excluded because of
368 missing data in the memory testing for the respective night. This was partly due to instances where
369 the testing was skipped because the patient had a seizure right before the scheduled testing and no
370 testing was possible, sometimes due to the medical routine in the monitoring unit not allowing the
371 research team to conduct the testing within the set time-window, sometimes due to patients’ refusal
372 to participate, and some data could not be collected because of technical problems with the
373 equipment. Thus, a total of 66 patients were excluded from analyses.

374 In the remaining sample of 40 patients, there were 2 patients where we analyzed night 3 instead of
375 night 2. According to the medical diagnoses in this sample, 31 patients were diagnosed with focal
376 seizures (14 temporal lobe, 14 frontal lobe, 12 other localization; 14 with clear lateralization to the
377 left hemisphere, 7 with a clear lateralization to the right hemisphere, and 5 with bilateral localization
378 – the rest remained with unclear lateralization), and 9 patients were diagnosed with generalized

379 seizures. The average age of onset of seizures among all patients was 22.30 years (SD=15.14).
380 Among people with epilepsy, there were 23 with abnormal findings in magnetic resonance imaging.
381 More details on the patients can be found in the supplementary data file.

382 The final sample of 40 patients consisted of 22 women who were on average 32.27 years old (SD
383 12.67) and the 18 men who were on average 32.33 years old (SD 15.16). The median score on the
384 Beck Depression Inventory was 7.5 (range 0-39).

385 **3.2 Medication, seizures, and slow-wave sleep**

386 Detailed information on specific medication (anti-seizure medication, psychoactive medication, and
387 other) taken by each participant in this study on the day of admission is given in the supplementary
388 excel file column K. On the day before the assessed night, there were 8 patients who did not take any
389 anti-seizure medication, 23 took one type, 7 took two types and 2 took three. Among all patients on
390 anti-seizure medication, the average drug load was 0.97 (SD 1.12). Regarding psychoactive
391 medication, 36 took none, two patients took one type, and two took three types of psychoactive
392 medication. Among all patients who took psychoactive medication, the average drug load was 1.51
393 (SD 1.24). In the assessed night, there were 6 patients with focal seizures who experienced at least
394 one seizure, of which 2 were tonic-clonic seizures. No patient with generalized seizures experienced
395 any seizures during the assessed nights. SWS in the examined night lasted on average for 78.43 min
396 (SD 48.41).

397 **3.3 Memory performance**

398 Table 1 shows the average memory performance in the three tasks of the whole sample. On average,
399 verbal memory for word-pairs and episodic memory for the virtual towns declined over night, while
400 procedural memory for the fingertapping sequences increased. Table 2 shows the same values
401 separately for patients with temporal lobe seizures vs. other seizures. These two groups differed only
402 by their baseline performance in the fingertapping triplets, but not in the overnight retention (delayed
403 performance differences are not significant after correcting for multiple comparisons).
404

405 **3.4 Regression models for memory performance**

406 Table 3 shows the results of the multiple linear regression models estimates for the three types of
407 memory outcome. None of the candidate variables significantly predicted overnight performance
408 changes for procedural memory. For verbal memory, the only significant predictor was the
409 occurrence of a tonic-clonic seizure, which significantly worsened the ratio of recalled words.
410 However, only 2 patients experienced tonic-clonic seizures, and this result must therefore be
411 interpreted with caution. We also observed a tendency for significantly lower verbal memory
412 retention with higher load of psychoactive medication, which was significant before but not after
413 correcting for multiple comparisons and which needs to be considered with caution because of the
414 small number of patients taking psychoactive medication. For episodic memory, the only significant
415 effect was the duration of epilepsy, which negatively impacted retention. However, an additional
416 analysis revealed that this effect might not be perfectly linear but worsening of memory retention
417 appears after epilepsy duration of 10 years (see Figure 5).

418 A trend could be observed for total duration of deep sleep and episodic memory, which was
419 significant before but not after correcting for multiple comparisons. Contrary to our hypothesis,
420 longer SWS duration was associated with a lower ratio of recalled episodic memory in the morning.

421 Another trend was observed for anti-seizure medication, which tended to have a beneficial effect on
422 episodic memory.
423 Table 4 shows the results of the multiple linear regression for EEG band power during SWS with a p-
424 value $<.100$.
425 The only one parameter turning out to be a significant predictor after correcting for multiple
426 comparisons for the retention rate of episodic memory was lower SWS alpha-band power in the
427 frontal right region (see Table 4).
428 Other trends observed in this memory domain were such that higher power over frontal left areas -
429 but lower power over the frontal right areas - in the sigma and beta band were associated with better
430 overnight retention (see Table 4). Additionally, higher delta power in the temporal left area, and
431 higher alpha power in the temporal right and central left area, were associated with better overnight
432 retention.
433 For the other memory types, only trends could be observed (see Table 4). For procedural memory, a
434 trend was observed over central regions in the theta and alpha band, with higher power over the left
435 central area and lower power over the right central area being associated with better over-night
436 retention. Another trend was observed for lower parietal left theta power during SWS being
437 associated with higher over-night retention.
438 For verbal memory, trends were small, with the only one with $p<.05$ (i.e., significant before but not
439 after correction for multiple comparisons) such that better overnight-retention was associated with
440 lower central right alpha band power during SWS (see Table 4).
441

442 **4 Discussion**

443 The present study sought to evaluate how overnight memory retention for procedural, verbal, and
444 episodic memory modalities were associated with SWS duration, medication, seizure occurrence,
445 duration of epilepsy, and EEG spectral properties of SWS in people with epilepsy.

446 **4.1 Duration of epilepsy**

447 Concerning episodic memory, the duration of epilepsy surfaced as a notable factor negatively
448 impacting memory retention. Interestingly, an additional analysis hinted at a nonlinear relationship,
449 suggesting that memory retention decline might manifest notably after an epilepsy duration of 10
450 years. The identification of a possible nonlinear relationship, with significant memory decline
451 observed after a duration of 10 years, corroborate with prior literature indicating no negative impact
452 of epilepsy duration on non-verbal memory retention (Fitzgerald et al., 2013; Jokeit, Hennric et al.,
453 2005). Nevertheless, our results are relevant given that an early age of seizure onset has been
454 associated with a high risk for cognitive impairment (Rayner et al., 2016). Furthermore, the duration
455 of epilepsy can indirectly impact memory performance and is affected by seizure frequency (Bergin
456 et al., 2000; Rayner et al., 2016). However, these longitudinal studies do not explain impaired
457 overnight retention as found in our study. We suggest that prolonged epilepsy duration manifests
458 itself in consolidated epilepsy networks that could lead to permanent alterations in sleep architecture,
459 including SWS, and subsequently affect overnight episodic memory retention.

460 **4.2 Seizures**

461 Regarding verbal memory, the occurrence of tonic-clonic seizures emerged as a significant predictor,
462 significantly worsening the ratio of recalled words. However, only two patients experienced tonic-
463 clonic seizures, limiting the generalizability of this result. It is important to note that analysis of any
464 type of seizures did not emerge with a comparable effect. The observed impact of tonic-clonic

465 seizures on verbal memory aligns with prior research suggesting that seizure activity can
466 detrimentally affect memory performance. However, the limited occurrences of tonic-clonic seizures
467 in our study cohort underscore the need for caution in generalizing this finding.

468 Early research on the effect of seizures found no effect of seizures occurring after learning on
469 subsequent recall performance (Bergin et al., 1995). Indeed, the type of seizure is important in this
470 respect as tonic-clonic seizures or generalized seizures might disrupt sleep more significantly than
471 focal seizures, and therefore decrease quality of sleep and subsequent memory consolidation
472 processes (Thompson, Pamela J. and Duncan, 2005). Furthermore, for verbal memory it was reported
473 that seizures during a 24h retention interval impair memory retention for left-sided but not right-sided
474 temporal lobe-epilepsy (Jokeit, H. et al., 2001). Thus, the type of seizures and nature of the epileptic
475 disorder moderates the interaction between seizures and memory retention.

476 **4.3 Medication**

477 Trends were observed linking anti-seizure medication to better overnight retention of episodic
478 memory. While high doses of anti-seizure drugs (Jokeit, Hennric et al., 2005) and a large number of
479 anti-seizure drugs (Lutz and Helmstaedter, 2005) negatively affect memory, positive effects of anti-
480 seizure medication have been documented (Czubak et al., 2010), up to the extent where forgotten
481 material was recovered thanks to initiation of pharmacological treatment (Midorikawa and
482 Kawamura, 2007). Some anti-seizure medications can also affect sleep architecture in various ways
483 (Liguori et al., 2021). Specifically, lamotrigine (N=4 in our sample) and oxcarbazepine (N=4 in our
484 sample) bear the risk of worsening sleep, levetiracetam (N=25 in our sample) was reported to have
485 no effect on sleep, while lacosamide (N=3 in our sample) and perampanel (N=2) might even improve
486 sleep (see supplementary table for full details on medications). Changes in SWS duration (increase or
487 decrease) or sleep quality due to medication side effects might influence memory consolidation in
488 people with epilepsy, depending on the type of medication (Feld et al., 2013). According to our data,
489 the positive trend observed for anti-seizure medication improving episodic memory retention was
490 accompanied by a trend of decreased memory performance with longer SWS duration, which
491 suggests that the potential impact of medication needs to be evaluated alongside with additional,
492 possibly independent effects of SWS duration.

493 Additionally, a trending association between higher psychoactive medication load and lower verbal
494 memory retention was observed. Although not statistically significant after multiple comparison
495 corrections and affected by a small number of patients under this medication, this trend implies a
496 potential influence of psychoactive medication on verbal memory but requires further investigation
497 with a larger sample size for validation. Previous studies exploring the relationship between
498 psychoactive medication and memory retention revealed differential effects of improvement or
499 impairment of memory depending on the type of medication (Doss et al., 2023). Our findings are
500 based on an overall drug load and are therefore mixing medications with diverse types of action
501 together, limiting the overall conclusion on a potential negative association between higher
502 psychoactive medication load and verbal memory. It is interesting to note that the trend for worse
503 memory retention with higher psychoactive drug load emerged in the absence of effects from
504 depressive symptoms, as the first line of interpretation would be that individuals taking
505 antidepressive medication (N=3 in our sample, 2 sertraline and 1 escitalopram) are most likely
506 depressed, and depression leads to worse memory retention (Dillon and Pizzagalli, 2018). Therefore,
507 it should be considered that memory impairment is more likely to be explained by a side effect of
508 SSRIs, especially escitalopram (Anagha et al., 2021). However, SSRIs taken by the patients in our
509 sample are rather associated with a positive impact on SWS. Also, a negative memory impact is

510 commonly reported after administration of sedative drugs such as benzodiazepines (Doss et al.,
511 2023), which were taken by N=2 patients in our patient sample (N=1 Triazolam, N=1 Clobazam).
512 Benzodiazepines suppress SWS (de Mendonça et al., 2023), which impacts memory negatively.
513 Another drug that could play a role in this respect is Quetiapine, as it was reported to negatively
514 impact memory (Mori et al., 2004) but it was also taken by only N=2 patients in our sample. The
515 effects of Quetiapine on sleep are controversially discussed (Lin et al., 2023) and there is indication
516 that it negatively impacts SWS (Monti et al., 2017). In conclusion, the sample size of patients taking
517 psychoactive drugs was too small to conduct further sub-analyses by type of medication.
518 Nevertheless, our results suggest that it might be important to control for concurrent effects of
519 psychoactive drugs when examining memory retention in people with epilepsy.

520 **4.4 SWS duration**

521 In this study, trends were observed linking a longer duration of SWS to worsening of retention of
522 episodic memory, but no effect of SWS duration was observed for procedural memory and verbal
523 memory. This finding in people with epilepsy contradicts previous research in healthy individuals,
524 wherein SWS is recognized to play a crucial role in memory consolidation (Rasch and Born, 2013).
525 Previous work in healthy populations documented the significant impact of longer duration of SWS
526 on better overnight memory retention (Diekelmann et al., 2012). This is especially true for
527 consolidation of declarative memory, which includes episodic and semantic memory (Diekelmann et
528 al., 2009). Episodic memory is more dependent on SWS (Berres and Erdfelder, 2021) than
529 procedural memory (Ackermann and Rasch, 2014). For non-verbal declarative memory, SWS
530 duration was reported to be clearly related to better over-night retention in people with epilepsy
531 (Sarkis et al., 2016). Thus, while our results regarding procedural memory are in line with previous
532 research in healthy controls, the lack of a link between SWS duration and verbal declarative memory
533 as well as a trend for a negative association between SWS duration and episodic memory retention is
534 unexpected.

535 People with epilepsy often experience disruptions in their sleep architecture (Bernard et al., 2023).
536 However, previous research found no correlation between nighttime sleep architecture or
537 interruptions of sleep and a 24h delayed recall of verbal and non-verbal memory in people with
538 epilepsy (Fitzgerald et al., 2013). This is in line with a study testing verbal memory with a word-pair
539 task in healthy controls, showing that interrupting SWS did not affect overnight memory retention
540 (Genzel et al., 2009). In contrast, among individuals with subjective cognitive complaints, which is a
541 risk factor for experiencing further decline to mild cognitive impairment, fragmented SWS is related
542 to poor verbal memory retention (Manousakis et al., 2019). When assessing verbal memory on the
543 day after the examined night, the percent of time spent in SWS correlated positively with
544 performance (van Schalkwijk et al., 2018).

545 While the result of the present analysis is only a trend, we speculate that longer SWS duration might
546 be a result of the fragmented episodes of deep sleep. In order to respond to the need for SWS, people
547 with epilepsy might present with more attempts to reach satisfying SWS, but because these SWS
548 episodes are often interrupted by epileptiform activity, this fragmentation leads to an overall longer
549 duration of SWS, which is not beneficial for memory consolidation. This speculation is supported by
550 previous findings relating frequent interictal spikes during non-REM sleep to a reduced homeostatic
551 decrease in the slope of sleep slow waves during the night and to reduced daytime learning (Boly et
552 al., 2017). We suggest that future studies investigate the fragmentation of SWS in people with
553 epilepsy in more detail, elucidating the potential interaction between SWS duration, fragmentation,
554 and memory effects.

556 4.5 Power spectra of SWS

557 While our data suggested trends for relationships between neural oscillations during SWS and
558 overnight memory retention, these associations did not consistently reach statistical significance.
559 Only the retention rate of episodic memory was significantly higher when alpha-band power in the
560 frontal right region was lower during slow-wave sleep. Interestingly, this was accompanied by a
561 trend of increased left-frontal alpha-band power being associated with higher memory retention.
562 Episodic memory consolidation during sleep is theorized to be reflected by a specific thalamic-
563 hippocampal-neocortical interplay that depends on exact timing of slow and fast oscillations
564 (Inostroza and Born, 2013; Klinzing et al., 2019). Alpha-band power has been linked previously to
565 neuronal memory reprocessing during SWS (Yordanova et al., 2012). Also in this previous study,
566 there was a stronger effect over the right hemisphere, but with increased alpha power being
567 correlated with better knowledge transformation. Since the alpha band with 8-12 Hz overlaps partly
568 with slow sleep spindles which also peak frontally (Anderer et al., 2001), it is plausible that the effect
569 found in the present study is explained by sleep spindles, rather than EEG background activity. Slow
570 spindles at 8-12 Hz occur during SWS and it was documented that increased slow spindle activity is
571 related to better declarative memory performance (Marshall et al., 2006). The relevance of alpha
572 activity during sleep was brought into context with the use- or experience-dependent theory of sleep
573 function (Yordanova et al., 2012). According to this theory, homeostatic responses during sleep are
574 related to learning before sleep (Borbély, 1982; Sejnowski and Destexhe, 2000), where the alpha
575 band is associated with motor learning (Salih et al., 2009). A left-over right dominance was
576 hypothesized to reflect the right-hand use in the experimental task (Yordanova et al., 2012), which is
577 in line with the situation presented in our episodic learning task. While we did not intentionally
578 include procedural learning, it might be that the keyboard-dependent navigation in the virtual town
579 with the right hand is reflected in the alpha-dependent consolidation.

580 This observation is partly in contradiction with an additional observation derived from the
581 fingertapping task. This task aimed at examination of procedural memory and was conducted with
582 the non-dominant left hand. Also in this task was a trend of central theta and alpha activity being
583 linked to better overnight consolidation, most of which significant before, but not after correction for
584 multiple comparisons. Here, the strongest association was represented by increased central left alpha
585 activity being linked to better memory consolidation. Interestingly, the tendency was such that
586 increased left-hemispheric but lower right-hemispheric activity was associated with better overnight
587 retention. We speculate that this finding reflects consolidation and replay of procedural memory over
588 the motor-cortex – however, the hemispheric pattern is similar to the episodic memory task, where
589 the other hand was used. This implies that the trending left-right asymmetry is not specific for a
590 memory modality. While our results must be interpreted with caution given the non-significance after
591 correction for multiple comparisons, we could speculate that the hemispheric pattern might reflect
592 overall memory processing during SWS which is not necessarily linked to the hand used in the task.

593 For verbal memory, the trends were all very weak but pointed to lower central right activity in the
594 delta, theta and alpha band being associated with better memory retention, which is in contrast with
595 earlier research pointing towards higher activity in a broad frequency range being associated with
596 better verbal memory retention (Holz et al., 2012). However, only left-hemispheric activity was
597 investigated in this study. Another recent study suggests that the difficulty of the task matters (Qian
598 et al., 2022). This recent finding related performance in easy declarative and procedural memory

599 tasks with lower relative power of alpha or theta, but for a difficult version higher relative alpha band
600 activity was associated with better performance.

601 **4.6 Limitations**

602 In view of the lack of associations with the parameters selected in this study it is possible that the
603 most important factor for impaired learning among people with epilepsy was not included in our
604 study. Specifically, in our study, we did not investigate interictal epileptiform discharges, which have
605 been shown to play an important role in accelerated long-term forgetting of verbal information for
606 intervals between 30min and 4 days (Fitzgerald et al., 2013). Future studies should analyze the
607 contribution of interictal epileptiform discharges in relation to the spectral content of SWS in more
608 homogeneous patient groups.

609 We were not able to control for all factors that might be considered a potential confounder. It is
610 possible that the baseline difference between people with temporal lobe seizures vs. other seizures in
611 the fingertapping task affected the overall result, although there was no such difference in the
612 overnight retention ratio between these subgroups. Another limitation is that results could be skewed
613 if the baseline intelligence was interacting with any of the parameters of interest. Unfortunately, we
614 did not have test for the IQ, nor was this information obtained during the standard testing procedure.
615 Furthermore, we did not distinguish patients with temporal lobe seizures from other subgroups, such
616 as frontal lobe seizures, because of the small sample size. Despite mostly verbal memory impairment
617 is best documented for temporal lobe seizures, memory impairment has also been observed in
618 patients with frontal lobe seizures (Centeno et al., 2010). However, verbal memory retention is
619 differentially affected by seizures in temporal lobe epilepsy depending on the lateralization of the
620 epileptic focus (Jokeit, H. et al., 2001). In sum, our results need confirmation in larger and more
621 homogeneous patient groups.

622 Concerning procedural memory, the study revealed that none of the candidate variables significantly
623 predicted changes in procedural memory performance overnight. However, it is essential to consider
624 the possibility of other unexamined variables or interactions that might contribute to procedural
625 memory processes, such as localization of seizures and interictal epileptiform activity.

626 In this study we identified slow-wave sleep segments manually and did not investigate other sleep
627 stages. Therefore, no further information on sleep architecture is available in the present work. In the
628 future, automated sleep scoring will most likely replace the time-consuming task of sleep staging
629 (Fiorillo et al., 2019). However, automated sleep scoring might not be accurate in epilepsy, as
630 epileptiform activity can represent confounders for algorithms that have been developed for sleep
631 staging in healthy individuals (Amin et al., 2023). The present approach is therefore preferable given
632 the current state of the art of sleep staging.

633 It would have been interesting to compare the group without an epilepsy diagnosis to patients
634 regarding their memory performance. However, after excluding participants in this sub-group with
635 missing data in the memory tests, only one participant was left, which did not allow for such an
636 analysis.

637 Although the current sample is large given the clinical limitations, further research with larger
638 cohorts, more homogeneous subgroups and longitudinal designs is warranted to validate these
639 findings and unravel the underlying mechanisms driving memory retention in people with epilepsy.
640 We could not investigate more subtypes of seizures and medications because of this limitation, which
641 represents an important limitation in the generalizability of the results.

642 **4.7 Conclusions**

643 The presented findings reveal relevance of epilepsy duration, medication, and SWS spectral contents
644 for specific forms of memory in people with epilepsy. While the relation between tonic-clonic
645 seizures and lower verbal memory retention was expected, a trending relation between extended
646 duration of SWS and a decrease in episodic memory retention was surprising but is possibly due to
647 fragmentation of SWS. Furthermore, the trends observed for positive effects of anti-seizure
648 medication on episodic memory retention but negative effects of psychoactive medication on verbal
649 memory retention warrant further investigation, given their potential relevance for
650 neuropsychological testing of epilepsy-related memory deficits. Finally, we deem the negative
651 association between frontal right SWS alpha activity and episodic memory interesting. This
652 frequency band is possibly reflecting the activity of slow sleep spindles, and further trends in our data
653 revealed an interesting asymmetrical pattern of higher left-sided and lower right sided frontal activity
654 in this frequency band being linked with better memory performance. Since motor consolidation
655 theories do not fully explain the pattern we found, we suggest investigating further the hemispheric
656 distribution of slow sleep spindles during SWS and their relation to memory performance in the
657 procedural and episodic domain.

658 **5 Conflict of Interest**

659 ET reports personal fees from EVER Pharma, Marinus, Arvelle, Angelini, Argenx, Medtronic, Bial-
660 Portela & C^a, New Bridge, SK, Pharma, GL Pharma, GlaxoSmithKline, Boehringer Ingelheim,
661 LivaNova, Eisai, UCB, Biogen, Sanofi, Jazz Pharma, and Actavis. His institution received grants
662 from Biogen, UCB Pharma, Eisai, Red Bull, Merck, Bayer, the European Research Council, Austrian
663 Research Fund (FWF), Bundesministerium für Wissenschaft und Forschung, and Jubiläumsfond der
664 Österreichischen Nationalbank. YH reports fees for lectures from Eisai. She received prior funding
665 from the Icelandic Research Fund, Austrian Research Fund, and the European Research Council.
666 FJvS and SE report no conflicts of interest.

667 **6 Author Contributions**

668 SE: Writing – review & editing, Investigation; ET: Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization,
669 Supervision, Resources; FJvS: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data
670 curation, Formal Analysis, Supervision; YH: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing,
671 Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Software, Visualization, Supervision, Project
672 administration, Funding acquisition;

673 **7 Funding**

674 This work was supported by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF): T 798-B27, the Research Fund of the
675 Paracelsus Medical University (PMU-FFF): A-16/02/021-HÖL, and the German Research
676 Foundation, Walter Benjamin program (DFG SCHA 2369/1–1; FJVS).

677 **8 Acknowledgments**

678 Thanks to the students Miriam Bacher, Nina Biller, Björn Butter, Lukas Christmann, Leonie Dehne,
679 Isabelle Ehrlich, Maike Engel, Sophia Gabler, Johannes Göller, Daniel Göller, Dirk Gütlin, Lilian
680 Gutsch, Viola Heberger, Lucie Knörr, Pascal Lempe, Johanna Luxbauer, Adrian Marcu, Valentina
681 Ostreljanovic, Lucas Rainer, Christoph Schabernag, Denise Schindlmaier, Ronny Sluka, Anja
682 Ströhlein, Marina Thierauf, Tamara Traub, Elisabeth Weingartner, and Philipp Windhager for help

683 with the intensive examination schedule. Thanks to Christina Florea, Bernhard Ganser, Constantin
684 Hecker, Magdolna Mezes, Tobias Moser, Zsolt Nagy, Caroline Neuray, Ferdinand Otto, Rudolf
685 Kreidenhuber, Alexander Kunz, David Gabelia, Alexandra Rohrer, Fabio Rossini, Markus
686 Leitinger, Judith Dobesberger, Julia Höfler, and Gudrun Kalss for help with recruitment and
687 providing informed consent. Thanks to Eydís Anna Guðmundsdóttir for pre-reviewing a couple of
688 night recordings. Thanks to Florian Hutzler for helping us with the extraction of parallel word lists
689 from the BAWL. Thanks to Michaela Pötzelsberger and the staff at the epilepsy monitoring unit for
690 help, support, and patience with our daily visits for examination, the weekly recruitment, and for
691 sharing their office space with the scientific staff.

692 **9 Supplementary Material**

693 Supplementary File 1 provides further demographic and medical details on patients in an excel table.

694 **10 Data Availability Statement**

695 Due to the sensitive nature of the data, the datasets generated for this study can be made available
696 upon reasonable request and after application and approval by the relevant ethical authority.

697

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955

956 **Figure Legends**

957 **Figure 1:** Repeated testing procedure with learning sessions, immediate recall (denoted as 1.1, 2.1, 3.1 etc.) and
958 delayed recall (denoted as 1.2, 2.2, 3.2, etc.).

959 **Figure 2:** Exemplary sequence for fingertapping. Numbers indicate the allocation of fingers to numbers required
960 to type the desired sequence, whereas letters indicate the keys on the keyboard used. Thus, for the illustrated

961 sequence, the fingers were moved in the following order: ring finger, middle finger, index finger, little finger,
962 ring finger.

963 **Figure 3:** Exemplary learning and recall scene for the wordpair task. During learning, pairs of words were
964 shown while during recall only the first word was shown, and the patients were asked to spell out the second
965 word. Correctness of their answer was noted down by an experimenter.

966 **Figure 4:** Outline of the paths for towns 3 and 5, studied in the evening of night 2 and 3, alongside with an
967 example of one scene. The scene in town 3 shows containers with a man cleaning the street in front of them, the
968 scene in town 5 shows a playground and a dog.

969 **Figure 5:** Relation between overnight memory retention for episodic memory and duration of epilepsy. Please
970 note that the scatterplot puts points that are horizontally or vertically at the exact same number (e.g. 0) slightly
971 displaced so the individual data points can be seen, this causes a point to appear before 0 years on the x-axis.
972
973

974 **Tables**

975
976 **Table 1:** Average memory performance in the three tasks for procedural memory (fingertapping),
977 verbal memory (word-pairs), and episodic memory (virtual reality town).

measure	<i>mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>median</i>	<i>range</i>
FT triplets immediate	72.03	36.30	75	2.67-153.33
FT triplets delayed	74.96	38.27	78	1-154
FT triplets ratio*	106.57	33.64	102.25	5.77-222.22
Word-pairs immediate	21.73	11.35	19	6-51
Word-pairs delayed	18.90	11.21	17	3-46
Word-pairs ratio*	85.12	19.03	92.58	30-111.11
Episodic immediate	41.45	14.92	42.5	3-74
Episodic delayed	34.63	17.39	35	8-82
Episodic ratio*	86.67	41.47	88.76	18.75-300

978 FT: Fingertapping; *ratio is represented as %: = delayed/immediate *100;

979

980
981 **Table 2:** Average memory performance in the three tasks for procedural memory (fingertapping),
982 verbal memory (word-pairs), and episodic memory (virtual reality town) separately for people with
983 temporal lobe seizures vs. other seizures. Descriptives are given as median/range and test values as
984 Mann-whitney U for ordinal variables (immediate, delayed) and as mean/SD and t-values for interval
985 variables (ratios and FT triplets).

measure	<i>Temporal lobe seizures</i>	<i>Other seizures</i>	<i>test value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
FT triplets immediate	90.21 (33.09)	62.24 (34.66)	-2.51	.018
FT triplets delayed	91.57 (36.48)	66.01 (36.82)	-2.11	.045
FT triplets ratio*	1.00 (0.12)	1.10 (0.41)	1.11	.274
Word-pairs immediate	20 (10-34)	16 (6-51)	178.5	.932
Word-pairs delayed	17.5 (3-33)	14 (3-46)	192.5	.777
Word-pairs ratio	0.81 (0.24)	0.87 (0.16)	0.79	.441
Episodic immediate	45.5 (25-66)	40 (3-74)	161.5	.570
Episodic delayed	29.5 (8-82)	39 (15-53)	162.5	.590
Episodic ratio*	0.84 (0.21)	0.88 (0.49)	0.36	.718

986 FT: Fingertapping; *ratio is represented as %: = delayed/immediate *100;

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989

990 **Table 3:** Regression results for overnight retention of procedural memory as fingertapping triplets,
991 verbal memory as word pairs, and episodic memory according to the virtual-reality test, predicted by
992 the variables depression (BDI), anti-seizure medication drug load, psychoactive medication drug
993 load, sex, SWS duration in minutes, seizure occurrence during retention night, tonic clonic seizure
994 occurrence during retention night, and duration of epilepsy as age at testing minus age of onset.

	<i>Regression coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
<u>FT triplets ratio*</u>				
BDI	-0.003	0.007	-0.369	.715
Anti-seizure medication drug load	0.012	0.059	0.210	.835
Psychoactive medication drug load	.004	0.110	0.038	.970
sex	-0.155	0.127	-1.219	.232
SWS duration	<.001	<.001	0.800	.430
Seizure in night	-0.060	0.205	-0.294	.771
Tonic clonic seizure in night	-0.087	0.361	-0.242	.810
Duration of epilepsy	-0.007	0.007	-1.006	.322
<u>Word pairs ratio**</u>				
BDI	-0.003	0.003	-0.786	.438
Anti-seizure medication drug load	-0.014	0.026	-0.545	.590
Psychoactive medication drug load	-0.111	0.050	-2.241	.032
sex	-0.056	0.057	-0.989	.330
SWS duration	<.001	<.001	0.823	.417
Seizure in night	0.139	0.092	1.515	.140
Tonic clonic seizure in night	-0.534	0.162	-3.292	.002
Duration of epilepsy	<.001	0.003	-0.021	.983
<u>Episodic memory ratio***</u>				
BDI	-0.008	0.008	-1.087	.286
Anti-seizure medication drug load	0.121	0.062	1.937	.062
Psychoactive medication drug load	-0.004	0.117	-0.039	.969
sex	-0.191	0.135	-1.416	.167
SWS duration	<.001	<.001	-2.118	.042
Seizure in night	-0.253	0.217	-1.163	.254
Tonic clonic seizure in night	0.466	0.383	1.216	.233
Duration of epilepsy	-0.021	0.007	-2.790	.009

995 FT: fingertapping; BDI: Beck depression inventory score; SWS: SWS
996 *triplets ratio model had a residual standard error: 0.3601 on 31 degrees of freedom
997 **word-pair ratio model had a residual standard error: 0.1616 on 31 degrees of freedom
998 ***episodic ratio model had a residual standard error: 0.3816 on 31 degrees of freedom
999 Bold font indicates significant results after correction for multiple comparisons.

1000
1001 **Table 4:** Regression results for overnight retention of procedural memory as fingertapping triplets,
1002 verbal memory as word pairs, and episodic memory according to the virtual-reality test, predicted by
1003 EEG power spectra. Only results with $p < .100$ are shown, see supplementary section for full list of
1004 coefficients and model residuals.

	<i>Regression coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
<u>FT triplets ratio</u>				
Parietal left theta	-3.513	1.711	-2.053	.049
Central left theta	2.765	1.127	2.453	.020
Central right theta	-2.178	1.104	-1.974	.058
Central left alpha	4.081	1.418	2.877	.007

Central right alpha	-4.359	1.785	-2.442	.021
<u>Word pairs ratio</u>				
Central left delta	0.257	0.137	1.881	.070
Central right delta	-0.300	0.174	-1.725	.095
Central right theta	-1.32	0.748	-1.766	.088
Temporal right alpha	-2.639	1.512	-1.745	.092
Central right alpha	-2.424	1.092	-2.218	.035
<u>Episodic memory ratio</u>				
Temporal left delta	0.783	0.330	2.373	.025
Frontal left alpha	5.517	2.617	2.108	.044
Frontal right alpha	-9.900	2.941	-3.367	.002
Temporal right alpha	5.763	2.568	2.244	.033
Central left alpha	2.920	1.475	1.980	.057
Frontal left sigma	7.459	3.749	1.990	.056
Frontal right sigma	-10.906	4.528	-2.408	.023
Frontal left beta	21.621	9.152	2.362	.025
Frontal right beta	-26.471	11.599	-2.282	.030

1005 FT: fingertapping; Bold font indicates significant results after correction for multiple comparisons.

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